

Regional Anatomical Study of Padu Varmam Points**K. Arumugam¹, A. Muneeswaran², N.V. Ganga³, Neil James⁴, M. HemaLatha⁵, C. Kalai Kumar⁶**¹Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli²Professor & HOD, Department of Varma Maruthuvam, Government Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai³Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Thoothukudi Medical College, Thoothukudi⁴Senior Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli⁶M.B.B.S, D. Ortho, Tutor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli

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Abstract:

Siddha is the traditional system of medicine which was followed and developed by various siddhars. Among them, Agathiyar is one of the notable siddhar who was dealt with varma Maruthuvam. Varma Maruthuvam is a system of medicine which is purely based on "Vaasi". Vaasi is the vital energy which is present from the beginning of foetal formation. This vital energy is omnipresence in human body. But the most important vital energy points were 108. The 108 varmam points were mainly classified into Padu Varmam and Thodu Varmam. Padu Varmam points are extremely subtle points of the body. This article will provide a thorough knowledge about the Padu Varmam point's locations, connected muscles, nerves and their arterial, venous supply. This study will be beneficial to further research.

Keywords: Siddha, Varmam, Vital energy, Padu Varmam, Anatomy.

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Introduction

Siddha medicine is practiced in South India and this system consists of three specialities such as Varmam, Yogam and Kayakarpam. Varmam is the branch of the siddha system which involves a special kind of therapy based on vital points called Varmam points present in the body.

Varmam means uyir aattral. Varmam points are the energy storage places from where the energy is transmitted to various parts of the body that regulate all the functions of the body.

There are about 108 varmam points in our body. These are classified into Padu varmam and Thodu varmam. The Padu varmam are 12 in number and Thodu varmam are about 96 in number.

Aim of the study

To locate the various padu varmam points anatomically and the various underlying structures.

Materials and Methods

During dissection session of 1st MBBS students in the department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli, the various Padu varmam points stated in various Siddha varma books were located and the underlying anatomical structures were studied.

Observations of various Padu varmam points**1) Thilartha varmam Synonyms**

Thilartha kaalam (Varma soothiram), Thilasa kaalam (Varma nithanam), Edaba (rhishaba) varmam (Varma panchekarana pinnal), Sthabani varmam (Varma vithi), Suzhi sarvanga adangal and A.L.H₆ (Anatomical name).

Location

- ½ inch below the midpoint of glabella which is an elevation in between the superciliary arch situated just above the supraorbital margin.
- Situated between the two eye brows at the intersection of frontal and nasal bones (Nasion).

Figure 1:

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Sensory innervation** – Infra-trochlear branch from naso-ciliary nerve which is the branch of ophthalmic nerve, a branch of Trigeminal nerve.

Figure 2:

- **Muscle** – Procerus muscle blends with medial end of frontal belly of occipito-frontalis muscle, and contraction produces transverse wrinkles on the bridge of nose.

Figure 3:

- **Vessels**
 - Artery – Angular artery (branch from facial artery) and dorsal nasal branch from ophthalmic artery.
 - Vein – Angular vein formed by union supratrochlear and supraorbital veins at the root of nose.

Figure 4:

2) Natchathira varmam

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Synonyms: Natchethira kaalam (Varma beerangi), Meena varmam (Varma panchekarana pinnal), Aabanga varmam (Varma vithi) & A.L4.H7 (Anatomical name)

Location: On the lateral border (canthus) of the eye

Figure 5:

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Bone** – Zygomatic bone
- **Sensory innervation** -Zygomatico-facial nerve branch of Maxillary nerve
- **Muscle** – Orbicularis oculi
- **Vessels**
Artery & Vein – Zygomatico-facial artery and vein

3) Sevikuthi Kaalam

Synonyms

Sevikuri varmam (Varma soodamani), Sevikutri varmam (Urpathi narambarai) ,Sirungadam (Varma vithi), L.C4.H8 (Anatomical name)

Location

Near the tragus of Ear

Anatomical structures underlying it

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- **Bone** – Condylar process of Mandible
- **Joint** – Capsule of Temporo – mandibular joint
- **Nerve** – Auriculotemporal nerve branch of anterior division of mandibular nerve
- **Muscle** – Tendon of Lateral Pterygoid
- **Vessel** – Superficial facial artery

4) Pidari varmam

Synonyms

Pidarikaalam (Varma saari), pidarisuzhi (or) pidarikuzhi and P.L.H₁₀ (Anatomical name).

Location

Junction of posterior aspect of neck and head, over External occipital protuberance.

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Bone** – Occipital bone
- **Nerve** – Greater occipital nerve(C2)
- **Muscle** – Semispinalis capitis
- **Vessel** – Occipital artery

5) Urakka Kaalam

Synonyms

Mathrika varmam, A.L2.N1 (Anatomical name)

Location

Situated 3 finger breadth below the chin and 2 finger breadth superolateral to thyroid cartilage (Adam’s apple).

Anatomical structures underlying it

- Nerve – Greater auricular nerve branch of cervical plexus (C2 & C3)
 - Muscle – Sternocleidomastoid
 - Vessels
- Vein – External jugular vein
 Artery – Carotid sinus (Dilatation at the beginning of bifurcation of common carotid artery)

6) Thummi varmam

Synonyms: Thivalai kaalam (Varma viralalavu nool), thivalai kuzhi varmam (Varma vilakkam), valavaama varmam (Sathuramani soothiram), midhuna varmam (Varma panchekarana pinnal), vaayu varmam (Paduvarma nithanam) and A.L.N6 (Anatomical name).

Location: One finger breadth above suprasternal space (At the upper border of manubrium of sternum between the sternal heads of sternocleidomastoid muscles).

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Muscle** – Sternothyroid
- **Nerve**
Transverse cervical nerve
- **Vessel**
Vein – Anterior jugular vein

7) Ner varmam

Synonyms: Ner varmam (Varma beerangi), Neru varmam (Varma odivu murivu sara soothiram), Koombu kuzhi varmam (Varma viralalavu nool), Karkadaga varmam (Varma panchekarana pinnal) & A.L.T₉ (Anatomical name).

Location: 10 finger breadth above the umbilicus, at the xiphoid process of sternum (lower end of sternum)

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Nerve** - Anterior cutaneous branch of 6th intercostal nerve
- **Muscle** - Transversus thoracis, Rectus abdominis and Diaphragm
- **Vessel**
Artery - Perforating branches from internal thoracic artery

8) Adappa Varmam Synonyms: Adappa kaalam (Varma beerangi), Adaippa varmam (Varma kannadi), Adappan kaalam (Varma gnana odivu murivu sara soothiram) A.L12.T3 [Anatomical name]

Location: 10 finger breadth lateral to the ner varmam or 4 finger breadth above the 11th floating rib at the 6th intercostal space.

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Nerve-** Lateral cutaneous branch from 6th intercostal nerve
- **Muscle –** Lattisimus dorsi, External abdominal oblique
- **Vessel**

Artery- Anterior intercostal artery & Musculo phrenic artery terminal branch of internal thoracic artery.

9) Urumi Varmam Synonyms: Urumi kaalam (Varma saari), Pandri varmam (Varma beerangi), Varma sakkira kaalam (Varma aani), Singu (Simma) varmam (Varma panchekarana pinnal) & A.L.A5 (Anatomical name)

Location: Located at the midpoint between xiphoid process and umbilicus, 4 finger breadth above umbilicus.

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Nerve** – Anterior cutaneous branch from 8th intercostal nerve
- **Muscle** – Interlacing of external and internal oblique aponeurosis.
- **Vessel**

Artery- Branches of anastomosis between superior epigastric and inferior epigastric artery

10) Periya atthi churukki varmam

Synonyms: Atthi churukki varmam (Varma laada soothiram), Valiya atthi churukki varmam (Varma soothiram), Churukki kaalam (Varma soothiram) and A.L12.A9 (Anatomical name).

Location: Two finger breadth below the 11th floating rib.

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Nerves** – Subcostal nerve
- **Muscle**- External and Internal oblique muscles and Transversus abdominis muscles
- **Vessel**

Artery- Subcostal artery.

11) siriya atthi churukki varmam

Synonyms: Siriya atthi churuki varmam (varma beerangi), Atthi churukki varmam (varma soodamani), Magara varmam (varma panchi karana pinnal) and A.L12.A10 (Anatomical name).

Location: Three fingers breadth below the tip of the 11th floating rib, one finger breadth below periya atthi churukki varmam.

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Nerves** – Subcostal nerve
- **Muscles** – External and Internal oblique muscles and Transversus abdominis muscles
- **Vessel**

Artery – Subcostal artery.

12) Kalladai kaalam

Location: Root of the scrotum, eight fingers breadth below the umbilicus.

Anatomical structures underlying it

- **Nerve:** Genital branch of Genitofemoral nerve
- **Vessels:** Testicular artery and venous plexus

Discussion

Varma and its manipulative techniques seem to be an important concern in today’s medical world. Varma, an easy and highly efficient art has been hidden from human community for various reasons. Hence the science behind this remains unknown. The basic work of finding the anatomical locations and the structures present in the padu varmam points is a simple step in this rigorous task. The naming of the padu varmam appears to correlate with the symptoms or the place where the points are located. Most of the padu varmam are paired and are closely related to the vital organs of the body; for example, the thilartha kaalam is related to brain; natchathira kaalam is related to the optic nerve and the vessels of

the eyes; sevikuttri kaalam is related to the nerves and vessels of the ear; urakka kaalam is related to the pharyngeal plexus and the salivary glands; thummi kaalam and thymus gland are closely related; ner varmam is directly associated with the heart and its blood vessels; periya atthi churukki and siriya atthi churukki are analogous with the liver and its associated structures; adappa kaalam is related to the lungs; the moothira kaalam corresponds to the urinary bladder; and the kallidai kaalam is related to the penis and scrotum. With this study, we were able to identify that the padu varmam points contain various important and imperative structures.

Conclusion

Padu varmam points are the high energy concentrated centres in the human body. These are the vital life centres. When these points are affected, it results in severe adverse effects which may lead to loss of consciousness or even death. These anatomical structures pave a path for the standardization of the locations of the Padu varmam points. Each Padu varmam when manipulated in an incorrect aspect gives specific symptoms. The way in which these symptoms occur can be studied in detail with reference of the anatomical structures.

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